

SINGLE CUBE APPARATUS – SHEAR PROPERTIES DETERMINATION AND SHEAR STRAIN VARIATION IN NATURAL DENSITY GRADIENT MATERIALS

BI Hassel¹, CS Modén², P Berard³ and LA Berglund⁴

¹ PhD student. Lab. of Structural Function. Kyoto University. RISH. Japan.

² PhD. Dept. of Aeronautical and Vehicle Engineer, Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden.

³ Post doctoral fellow. Lab. of Sustainable Materials, Kyoto University. RISH. Japan.

⁴ Professor. Dept. of Fibre and Polymer Technology, Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden. *Email address:* blund@kth.se (L.A. Berglund)

SUMMARY

Transversal shear of softwoods was studied with the single cube apparatus (SCA). Full field strain data and FEA were used to validate the device. Once a close to pure shear strain region was confirmed, the relationship between shear strain and radial density gradient was obtained; finally an improved FE model was created.

Keywords: Anisotropy, Density gradient, Digital speckle photography, Shear properties, Shear testing.

INTRODUCTION

Shear properties remain the main challenge in testing anisotropic materials. The combination of high axial modulus (E_L) and low density make Norwegian spruce (*Picea abies*) an efficient lightweight beam structures. We focus on the transverse radial-tangential plane (RT) of this specie (Figure 1) where the characteristic wood moduli in radial (E_R), tangential (E_T) and shear ($G_{RT} = G_{TR}$) are quite low since cell wall bending contributes significantly to deformation [1,2]. Glulam beams present large variations in local transverse strain, due to low transverse shear modulus (G_{RT}) [3,4]. Shear coupling is a very important effect [5], caused by the combination of low shear modulus G_{RT} and the slanted annual ring orientation. Even if global transverse loads are in-plane tension or compression, large in-plane shear strains (ϵ_{RT}) dominate the overall deformation. As the experimental shear measurements present serious difficulties, there is a limited literature on shear behavior of wood. Several shear testing devices have been developed. The fixture developed by Arcan et al. [6], is a time consuming procedure since the specimen needs to be bonded to the test fixture by the use of adhesive. Yen et al. [7] modified the Arcan device to eliminate the adhesive requirement. Further modification was done by Liu et al. [8] in order to study shear strength and modulus of solid wood. The method is hampered by a complex fixture and sample geometry of small thickness. The Iosipescu test, for determination of transverse shear properties in wood was originally developed for isotropic materials [9], and modified by Adams and Walrath [10] to use it for fiber composite materials. Pierron [11] pointed out that the shear stress- and strain-fields are neither pure nor homogeneous between the

notches and through the thickness, and demonstrated that strain inhomogeneities are caused by Saint-Venant effects, due to the short distance between loading points and notches. Xavier et al. [12,13] also applied the Iosipescu test to wood, and concluded that the apparent shear modulus obtained required correction based on finite element analysis. Finally, the Iosipescu method applied to wood includes the use of strain gauges, a complex fixture and specimen's geometry. Seichepine [14] developed a new device applicable also to shear tests. The method uses cubic specimens to determine elastic properties of anisotropic solids. The wood specimens are prepared with the material directions (L, T and R) parallel to the cube's edges. Vittecoq et al. [15] applied this method to unidirectional glass fiber composites, which produced in-plane shear stress parallel to the faces of a cubic sample, and a negligible compression stress. Berard et al. [16] introduced significant modifications to the method device developed by Seichepine.

The improved fixture by Berard et al. [16] is used in this study, and it is termed the single cube apparatus (SCA). Finite element analysis of the original apparatus revealed that the stress was not sufficiently homogeneous in the region where shear strains were measured. The SCA provides a more homogeneous shear field over a larger area in the specimens, as confirmed by finite element analysis (FEA). Previous experiments done by Berard et al. [16] and Hassel et al. [17] showed that all the elastic properties of an orthotropic material can be obtained from one SCA specimen. The SCA is then used to study the characteristic annual ring structure of Norwegian spruce (*Picea abies*) [18] which consists of well-defined regions of low and high density (earlywood and latewood), like many softwoods. The transition of these two regions within an annual ring is gradual and defines the anatomy of the transverse plane of a tree, combining liquid transport functions in the earlywood and load-carrying functions in the latewood.

Rough estimate of average relative density is not enough to understand how wood cell structure influence transverse elastic properties. A deeper understanding of the variation of material properties at the annual ring scale is needed. Modén and Berglund [19] demonstrated that the elastic deformation in the radial direction of softwoods is influenced by cell wall stretching, besides the bending contribution identified by Gibson and Ashby [2]. Local radial modulus E_R determined within each annual ring was later used to develop an improved micromechanical elasticity model for the radial and tangential properties of softwoods [20]. We focused on the transverse shear behavior of softwoods. No studies that combine local density measurements with local property and local full-field strain measurements were found. Furthermore, no previous studies have focused on local shear modulus, G_{RT} , at the annual ring scale. Aiming to develop a micromechanical model in which the shear modulus is related to the density gradient in the annual ring. The model is combined with FEA, which might help us improving the understanding of the low transverse shear modulus in spruce.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Single Cube Apparatus

Nine specimens of Norwegian spruce with average moisture content (MC) of 9.2 % were cut to cubes of 40 mm +/- 0.5 mm edge length. The edges were parallel to the wood natural

axes. A random black speckle pattern was sprayed to the radial-tangential plane (RT-plane) and specimens were tested to shear. The density at testing conditions was $451.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

The working mechanism of the SCA can be observed in Figure 2. The upper cross-head of the testing machine applies a compression load to the movable part of the apparatus (A). Through the grips (B) the load is transmitted to the specimen as shear forces. Small cylinders (C) ease the alignment. Based on FEA [16] a 31° angle between the loading direction and the specimen edge direction make up the geometry of the device. The $F\cdot\cos 31^\circ$ component of the load (F) is the shear force acting on the specimen. The $F\cdot\sin 31^\circ$ force component is transmitted through the large cylinders (D) maintaining a constant distance of 40 mm between upper and lower specimen grips (E). All cylinder surfaces are bright-polished in order to avoid friction stresses during rotation. Six planes are possible to be tested: RT, TR, LT, TL, LR and RL. The first letter corresponds to the shear component and the second one to the perpendicular direction to the load in the observed plane.

A 500 N-capacity load cell was used to apply a compression load (F) to the SCA with an Instron universal machine at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Digital Speckle Photography (DSP) was used to monitor the strains, using the measuring system GOM Aramis 1.3 m. Each sample was tested twice in the linear domain. First capturing the whole surface of the cube (40 mm x 40 mm) (*whole-area* case). Then, placing the camera closer to capture an average of four annual rings per image (*close-up* case), (10 mm x 10 mm) (Figure 3). Post-processing included cropping a central area of 13 mm x 5 mm.

To calculate the effective global shear stress formula (1) is used, where F is the load measured by the load cell of the Instron machine, A is the area of the plane in the cube (40 mm x 40 mm) submitted to shear load. Shear moduli, offset yield strain and offset yield strength for both specimen orientations (G_{RT} and G_{TR}), see Figure 1b-c, were calculated from the τ - γ curves in the linear region [21].

To analyze the SCA fixture, a FEA model was developed using ABAQUS. The model is composed of two dimensional quadratic shell elements. The majority is reduced integration 8-node rectangular elements with 5 degrees of freedom per node, S8R5. Some elements are triangular 6 node reduced integration elements with 5 degrees of freedom per node, STRI65, in order to facilitate meshing. The material is linearly elastic, with the elastic constants $E_R = 1200 \text{ MPa}$, $E_T = 800 \text{ MPa}$ and $\nu_{RT} = 0.35$ (Shispha and Berglund [5]). The value of G_{RT} was set to 60.8 MPa corresponding to the experimental results. The boundary condition set no restriction on shear degrees of freedom, are simply supported. A 0.5 mm constant displacement was induced, coincident with the experimental elastic tests.

Shear Modulus-Density Gradient Relationship

As elastic loads were applied, the density profile was obtained from the same samples. The radial variations in wood density were measured with the SilviScan-3 at STFI-Packforsk in Stockholm [22]. From the tested cubic samples, strips were cut with the same length of the side of the cube (radial direction, 40 mm), 2 mm thick (tangential direction) and 7 mm high (longitudinal direction). Density was measured every 50 μm .

Finite Elements Model Including Density Profile at the Annual Ring Scale

The FE model as previously explained was used, but including the density data from the SilviScan measurements. Material data are assigned to each node depending on the radial coordinate. This is a simplification, as it neglects the annual rings curvature and the fact that the rings have different widths at different tangential coordinates. Figure 4 shows the finite elements predictions for the shear strain distribution in the whole specimen.

Material Model

The material is modeled as a honeycomb deforming in both bending and stretching of the cell walls. The model relates density of the wood material, ρ , to relative elastic constants, E_T , E_R , ν_{RT} and G_{RT} . The same micro-mechanics material model developed by Modén and Berglund [20] was used. Derived from Master and Evans [23], based on principles of Gibson and Ashby [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a compressive load was applied through the grips of the SCA the central region of the cube specimen is subjected to homogeneous shear strain, as also concluded by Berard [16]. Outside this central region, the strain levels decrease. High local strains are present in close to the fixture edges. The strain field of a homogenized wood specimen based on finite element analysis is presented in Figure 5a. The homogeneous central strain region predicted by FEA is supported by DSP data. Unlike other testing devices discussed in the introduction section, the SCA specimens do not twist out-of-plane and the coupling effects are eliminated.

Specimens were tested in RT- and TR orientations (Figure 1b, c). An ideal homogeneous orthotropic material has the same in-plane shear modulus for two orientations ($G_{RT} = G_{TR}$), as a consequence of the elasticity theory. However the RT-oriented specimens presented lower shear modulus ($G_{RT} = 60.8$ MPa, $G_{TR} = 68.0$ MPa), with a lower standard deviation (9.6% versus 32.6%). The $G_{TR} > G_{RT}$ is explained by the stiffening effect from the annual ring curvature on G_{TR} and the different number of annual rings included in the average. Wood shows polar orthotropy [5] and in the TR case, the material axes (T, R) are slightly curved with respect to the shearing direction. RT-specimen orientation is recommended for determination of transverse shear modulus.

The selection of the “masked” area to accurately estimate the shear modulus was justified by the strain distribution results in Figure 5. The shear stress τ is constant over a region between the radial coordinates 14 mm and 26 mm and then reduced toward the edges (Figure 6). Consequently the average stress in the central region is higher than the effective global stress (horizontal line Figure 5). The accuracy of G_{RT} is improved when determining τ by FEA. Thus it is recommended to multiply the effective global stress by a correction factor of 1.16.

The deformation in the central area is almost pure shear. This is supported by the fact that shear strain (ϵ_{RT}) below the “yield strength” dominates completely and is larger than strains in radial or tangential directions (ϵ_R and ϵ_T), as seen in Figure 7. The ratios $\epsilon_{RT} / \epsilon_T$ and $\epsilon_{RT} / \epsilon_R$ are 9 and 150 respectively. These values were confirmed by FEA, $\epsilon_{RT} / \epsilon_T = 225$ and $\epsilon_{RT} / \epsilon_R = 30$. Local density at the scale of millimeters varies dramatically, and this will strongly

influence local deformation. The distribution of density, in the annual rings of Figure 4b ranges from 270 kgm^{-3} to 1030 kgm^{-3} , with a corresponding experimental shear strains varying from 0.0105 to 0.0009. The annual ring width is between 2 and 3 mm. The large variation in density illustrates the limitations of the average density concept in softwoods.

The predicted shear strain field from FEA agrees very well with the DSP data, as seen in Figures 4a and 4b. Annual ring scale variations in shear strain are plotted together with local density in Figure 8. Strains are extremely high in the lowest density regions, and quite sensitive to moderate increases in local density, becoming negligible in the highest density regions. The shear strain depends on shear modulus, and thus relative density, in a reciprocal manner, as expressed by the micromechanical model [24]. The maximum shear strain often appears at a small distance into the earlywood, rather than at the interface. This might be related to the formation of the wood in the early spring.

The FEM for the spruce wood specimen is based on the density profile from the SilviScan measurements. The micromechanical model relates the relative density profile within an annual ring to a corresponding set of density-dependent stiffness parameters (E_R , E_T , G_{RT} , ν_{RT}). FEM results give a strong correlation between the predicted and the measured shear strains at the annual ring scale. It seems that careful characterization of annual ring scale density distribution of softwoods in combination with the present model could be used to predict local and therefore global G_{RT} quite accurately. Density data shows that spruce have locally low density values. This explains why spruce can show very low G_{RT} ($G_{RT} \propto (\rho/\rho_s)^3$). In fact, the functional gradient of spruce can cause it to have lower G_{RT} than softwoods of the same average density but with different earlywood and latewood regions, i.e. pine (*Pinus sylvestris*).

CONCLUSIONS

The single cube apparatus (SCA) method was studied for testing wood in transverse shear. DSP was used to measure the full field ϵ_{RT} and the homogenized shear stress distribution was evaluated by FEA. A large central region of homogeneous and close to pure shear strain was found on the samples, making the SCA method a strong candidate for improved shear testing procedures in wood and other materials, where porosity (gripping problems), heterogeneity and polar orthotropy may cause difficulties. The specimen fabrication is simpler when compared with complex fixtures such as Arcan or Iosipescu. The G_{RT} on Norwegian spruce was determined as 71 MPa.

The low transverse shear modulus, G_{RT} , of spruce is related to its functional gradient structure and a micromechanical wood cell model. Agreement between high-resolution measured data and computed shear strains are accomplished. G_{RT} shows low values, this is explained by the micromechanical model, which proves that shear loading of a hexagonal honeycomb involves mainly cell wall bending rather than stretching. Furthermore, a thin low-density region close to the latewood-earlywood interface dominates the shear deformation in an annual ring, due to a strong correlation between shear strain and density.

Figure 1 a) Main directions in a tree stem. b) G_{RT} orientation. c) G_{TR} orientation.

a)

b)

Figure 2 a) Photograph of the single cube apparatus (SCA) with a in the Instron machine. RT-sample. b) Drawing of the SCA. The depth of B and E components is 55 mm, and that of C and D is 70mm.

Figure 3 Transverse plane of the SCA specimen in the test fixture. Note grip locations. The white dotted rectangle shows the whole-area case. The black dashed rectangle, the close-up case. Experimental strain and density profiles are obtained along the black solid line.

Figure 4 a) Shear strain field of the whole SCA specimen, as predicted based on the FEM, measured density distribution and micromechanical model. b) Shear strain field from the DSP close-up strain measurement (area enclosed in the dark-dashed square in Figure 7).

Figure 5 a) FEA results for the in-plane shear strain field. b) Filtered DSP strain field of a sample sheared in the RT-plane.

Figure 6 Shear stresses τ from FEA at 0.5 mm displacement as a function of radial coordinate at the center of the specimen. Effective global shear stress (horizontal line).

Figure 7 Applied load versus ϵ_R , ϵ_T , ϵ_{RT} . The picture number is directly related to the external load-strain curves.

Figure 8 Density distribution profile from SilviScan measurements and experimentally determined shear strain profile from the DSP measurements for *close-up* case.

$$\tau = \frac{F \cdot \cos 31^\circ}{A} \quad (1)$$

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Support from Kyoto University Foundation for travel expenses. Financial support from Professor Kohei Komatsu and the Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (Monbukagakusho), is gratefully acknowledged (IH). In addition, CM and LB gratefully acknowledge financial support from BiMaC, Vinnova and CEI-Boise.

References

1. Gibson LJ, Ashby MF. Cellular Solids: Structure and Properties, Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1988.
2. Modén CS, Berglund LA. A two-phase annual ring model of transverse anisotropy in softwoods. *Composite Science and Technology*, 2008; 68:3020-3026.
3. Aicher S, Dill-Langer G. Influence of cylindrical anisotropy of wood and loading conditions on off-axis stiffness and stresses of a board in tension perpendicular to grain. *Otto-Graf-Journal, Universität Stuttgart*, 1996; 7: 216-242.
4. Hoffmeyer P, Damkilde L, Pedersen TN. Structural timber and glulam in compression perpendicular to grain. *Holz als Roh- und Werkstoff*, 2000; 58: 73-80.
5. Shipsa A, Berglund LA. Shear coupling effects on stress and strain distributions in wood subjected to transverse compression. *Composite Science and Technology*, 2007; 67:1362-1369.
6. Arcan M, Hashin Z, Voloshin A. A method to produce uniform plane-stress states with application to fiber-reinforced materials. *Experimental Mechanics*, 1978; 18:141-146.
7. Yen SC, Craddock JN, The KT. Evaluation of a modified Arcan fixture for the in plane shear test of materials. *Experimental techniques*, 1988; 12: 22-25.
8. Liu JY, Ross RJ, Rammer DR. Improved Arcan shear test for wood, USDA Forest Service, Forest Products Laboratory. In: Gopu, Vijaya KA., ed. *Proceedings of the International Wood Engineering Conference*. New Orleans, LA. Baton Rouge, LA: Louisiana State University, 1996; 2:85-90.
9. Iosipescu N. New accurate procedure for single shear testing of metals. *Journal of Materials*, 1967; 2:537-566.
10. Adams DF, Walrath DE. Further development of the Iosipescu shear test method. *Experimental mechanics*, 1987; 27:113-119.
11. Pierron F. Saint-Venant effects in the Iosipescu specimen. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1998; 32:1986–2015.

12. Xavier J.C., Oliveira M., Morais J.L., Camanho P.P., Pierron F. Measurement of shear modulus of wood *pinus pinaster ait.* by Iosipescu test: numerical aspects. Livro de Actas do VII Congresso Nacional de Mecânica Aplicada e Computacional, Universidade de Évora, Portugal, 2003; I:551-560.
13. Xavier JC, Garrido NM, Oliveira M, Morais JL, Camanho PP, Pierron F. A. Comparison between the Iosipescu and off-axis shear test methods for the characterization of *Pinus Pinaster Ait.* Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2004; 35: 827-840.
14. Seichepine JL. Mise au point d'une méthode expérimentale destinée à l'identification de la matrice des complaisances élastiques de solides anisotropes. Application au bois. Thesis, Nancy, I.N.P.L., France, 1980.
15. Vittecoq E, Degallaix-Moreuil S, Degallaix G. Cisaillements inter- et intralaminaires de composites verre/époxyde unidirectionnel. Revue des Composites et des Matériaux avancés, Hermès SC. Pub., 2001; 11:303-322.
16. Berard P, Yang P, Yamauchi H, Umemura K, Kawai S. Modeling of cylindrical LVL: Finite elements models of a flat interlocked LVL and a comparison of standard and non standard testing methods in the elastic domain. In: Proceedings of the 2nd International Symposium on Veneer Processing and Products, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada, Ed.Dai, C. 2006. p. 428–435.
17. Hassel I, Berard P, Komatsu K. Development of wooden block shear wall – Improvement of stiffness by utilizing elements of densified wood. *Holzforschung*, 2008; 62:584-590.
18. Hassel BI, Berard P, Modén CS, Berglund LA. The single cube apparatus for shear testing – full-field strain data and finite element analysis of wood in transverse shear. *Composites Science and Technology* 2008. In Press.
19. Modén CS, Berglund LA. Elastic deformation mechanisms of softwoods in radial tension - Cell wall bending or stretching? *Holzforschung* 2008, 62:562-568.
20. Modén CS, Berglund LA. A two-phase annual ring model of transverse anisotropy in softwoods. *Composites Science and Technology* 2008; 68:3020-3026.
21. Hertzberg RW. Deformation and fracture mechanics of engineering materials. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 1996.
22. Lundqvist S-O, Hansson Å, Olsson L. SilviScan measurements on Maritime pine. STFI-Packforsk, report no 326, Stockholm 2007.
23. Masters IG, Evans KE. Models for the elastic deformation of honeycombs. *Composite Structures*, 1997;35:403-422.
24. Hassel BI, Modén CS, Berard P, Berglund LA. Functional gradient effects explain the low transverse shear modulus in spruce - Full-field strain data and a micromechanics model.